

Studies in the synthesis of Coumarino- α -pyrone and Furocoumarins : Part V. Kostanecki-Robinson Acylation of 7-Hydroxy- 6-acyl-8-methyl-4-alkyl or Arylcoumarins

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Kostanecki-Robinson acylation of 7-hydroxy-6-acyl-8-methyl-4-alkyl or arylcoumarin derivatives gave the corresponding coumarino- γ -pyrones (I), while 7-hydroxy-6-benzoyl-4,8-dimethylcoumarin gave the corresponding coumarino- α -pyrone (II). Structures are confirmed on the bases of IR spectra.

Kostanecki-Robinson reaction¹ on *o*-hydroxy aromatic ketones is known to give chromones² or coumarins³ depending upon the ketone and experimental conditions. Limaye and Ghate⁴ studied the Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation of 7-hydroxy-8-ethyl-6-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin and isolated two products viz., 4,4'-dimethyl-8-ethyl-coumarino-7,6- α -pyrone and 2',4-dimethyl-8-ethyl-3'-acetylcoumarino-7,6- γ -pyrone.

We have investigated the Kostanecki-Robinson acylation of several 7-hydroxy-6-acyl-8-methylcoumarin derivatives to synthesise coumarino- α -pyrones and coumarino- γ -pyrones, the structures of which were assigned on the basis of their IR spectra. These *o*-hydroxyketones were prepared by the Fries migration of 7-acyloxy-8-methylcoumarin derivatives and are described in the part IV⁵ where they are used in the preparation of psoralene derivatives.

7-Hydroxy-6-acetyl-4,8-dimethylcoumarin⁶ when subjected to Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate gave a product which was insoluble in cold dilute alkali and did not develop any colouration with ferric chloride solution. The IR spectrum showed three strong bands in the carbonyl region viz., 1745 cm^{-1} (lactonyl $> \text{C} = \text{O}$ group), 1690 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl $> \text{C} = \text{O}$ group) and 1650 cm^{-1} (acetyl group at position 7). On the basis of the IR spectra and analytical results, the compound has been assigned 7-acetyl-4,8,10-trimethyl-2H, 6H-pyrano(3,2-*g*)benzopyran-2,6-dione structure (Ia). Attempts to deacetylate this either by sodium carbonate or conc. sulphuric acid met with failure. 7-hydroxy-6-acetyl-4-phenyl-8-methyl on similar Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation afforded 7-acetyl-8,10-dimethyl-4-phenyl-2H, 6H-pyrano(3,2-*g*) benzopyran-2,6-dione (Ib), carbonyl absorption in the I.R. region 1745 cm^{-1} (lactonyl $> \text{C} = \text{O}$ group), 1690 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl

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(b). W. Baker and R. Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **127**, 1981.

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3. R. W. Cantor, A. R. Martin and A. Robertson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1877.

4. D. B. Limaye and I. Ghate, *Rasayanam*, 1939, **1**, 169.

5. Part IV. *This Journal* (Accompanying paper).

6. S. Rangaswami and T. R. Seshadri, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1938, **7A**, 8.

> C = O group) and 1650 cm^{-1} (acetyl group at position 7. 7-hydroxy-6-propionyl-4,8-dimethylcoumarin and 7-hydroxy-6-propionyl-8-methyl-4-phenylcoumarin on similar acetylation gave (Ic) and (Id) respectively while 7-hydroxy-6-benzoyl-4,8-dimethylcoumarin gave 4,10-dimethyl-6-phenyl-2H, 8H-pyrano (3-2-g)benzopyran-2,8-dione (II) and its acetyl derivative.

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| I a. R = R ₂ = CH ₃ ; R ₁ = COCH ₃ | e. R = CH ₃ , R ₁ = H, R ₂ = C ₆ H ₅ |
| b. R = Ph, R ₁ = COCH ₃ , R ₂ = CH ₃ | f. R = R ₂ = C ₆ H ₅ , R ₁ = H |
| c. R = R ₁ , R ₂ = CH ₃ | g. R = R ₂ = C ₆ H ₅ , R ₁ = CH ₃ |
| d. R = Ph, R ₁ = R ₂ = CH ₃ | |

7-Hydroxy-6-acetyl-4,8-dimethylcoumarin and 7-hydroxy-6-acetyl-8-methyl-4-phenylcoumarin on Kostanecki-Robinson benzoylation with benzoic anhydride and sodium benzoate gave 4,10-dimethyl-8-phenyl-2H, 6H-pyrano(3-2-g) benzopyran-2,6-dione (Ie) and 10-methyl-4,8-diphenyl-2H, 6H-pyrano(3-2-g) benzopyran-2,6-dione (If) respectively. Carbonyl absorption in the IR. region 1745 cm^{-1} (lactonyl) > C = O group) and 1680 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl > C = O). No 7-benzoyl derivative could be isolated in these two cases. 7-hydroxy-6-propionyl-4-phenyl-8-methylcoumarin on Kostanecki-Robinson benzoylation afforded (Ig).

Attempt to prepare (Ie) and (Ig) from 7-hydroxy-6-acetyl-4,8-dimethyl and 7-hydroxy-6-propionyl-4-phenyl-8-methylcoumarin by modified Baker-Venkatraman transformation by refluxing the *o*-hydroxy ketone with benzoylchloride, potassium carbonate in acetone according to Seshadri *et al.*⁷ gave only the *o*-benzoyl derivative of the ketones. Carbonyl absorption in the IR. region 1760 cm^{-1} (lactonyl > C = O group), 1730 cm^{-1} (benzoyl ester > C=O group) and 1690 cm^{-1} (aromatic ketone).

EXPERIMENTAL

Infrared spectra (nujol) were determined with a Perkin Elmer 237 grating spectrophotometer. All m.ps. are uncorrected.

Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation: A mixture of *o*-hydroxyketone (1 g.), freshly fused sodium acetate (2 g.) and acetic anhydride (10 ml.) was heated at 180° - 90° in an oil bath for 10 to 12 hrs. After cooling the reaction mixture was poured into water and filtered. The residue was washed with dilute alkali and then with water. The product was finally crystallised from acetic acid. M.P., yields etc. are recorded in Table I.

Kostanecki-Robinson benzoylation: A mixture of *o*-hydroxyketone (1 g.), freshly fused sodium benzoate (2 g.) and benzoic anhydride (3 g.) was heated at 180°–90° in an oil bath for 10–12 hrs. The reaction mixture was worked up as above and the product crystallised from acetic acid. M.P., yields etc. are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Compound	M.P. °C	Yield (g)	Molecular formula	Analysis			
				Found Carbon %	Found Hydrogen %	Required Carbon %	Required Hydrogen %
Ia	250	0.4	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₅	68.81	4.97	68.48	4.70
Ib	266	0.5	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₅	73.01	4.34	73.3	4.44
Ic	259	0.5	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₄	70.96	5.21	71.11	5.18
Id	247	0.6	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₄	75.6	4.34	75.9	4.8
Ie	304	0.4	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₄	75.26	4.34	75.48	4.4
If	276	0.4	C ₂₅ H ₁₆ O ₄	79.05	4.4	78.95	4.4
Ig	281	0.5	C ₂₆ H ₁₈ O ₄	79.16	4.34	79.2	4.6

4,10-Dimethyl-6-phenyl-2H, 8H-pyrano(3,2-g)benzopyran-2-8-dione (II): A mixture of 7-hydroxy-6-benzoyl-4,8-dimethylcoumarin (0.5 g.), freshly fused sodium acetate (1.0 g.) and acetic anhydride (3 ml.) was heated at 180°–90° in an oil bath for 8–9 hrs. The reaction mixture was worked up as above. The product was found to be a mixture of two compounds. The separation of these was effected by the treatment with hot ethanol. The product, which remained insoluble in ethanol, was crystallised from acetic acid in colourless needles, m.p. 258°. Yield 0.2 g. (Found: C, 75.41; H, 4.74%; C₂₀H₁₄O₄ required C, 75.48; H, 4.40%).

The alcoholic mother liquor on cooling deposited the crystals of 7-acetoxy-6-benzoyl-4,8-dimethylcoumarin, m.p. 178°. Yield 0.1 g. (Found: C, 71.32; H, 4.64%. C₂₀H₁₆O₅ requires C, 71.44; H, 4.76%).

7-Benzoyloxy-6-acetyl-4,8-dimethylcoumarin (Ic): A mixture of 7-hydroxy-6-acetyl-4,8-dimethylcoumarin (0.5 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (1.0 g.), benzoyl chloride (0.5 ml.) and acetone (30 ml.) was refluxed on water bath for 35 hrs. On working up the reaction mixture as usual gave the product 7-benzoyloxy-6-acetyl-4,8-dimethylcoumarin which was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 240°. Yield 0.4 g. (Found: C, 71.90; H, 4.74%. C₂₀H₁₆O₅ requires C, 71.44; H, 4.76%).

Similarly 7-benzoyloxy-6-propionyl-4-phenyl-8-methylcoumarin was obtained under above conditions, m.p. 160°. (Found: C, 75.47; H, 4.55%. C₂₅H₂₀O₅ requires C, 75.0; H, 5.0%).

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